

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	R-N-OH		R-N-O	
	R	R'	HtOH (nm)	Triazen oxide (II) log ε
1.	OH ₂	2'-anthraquinonyl	342 420	4.318 4.029
2.	O ₂ H ₆	2'-anthraquinonyl	342 418	4.107 3.798
3.	O ₆ H ₈	2'-anthraquinonyl	352 420	4.438 4.207
4.	O ₆ H ₈	o-carboxyphenyl	218 242 266	4.401 4.365 4.531
5.	OH ₂	o-nitrophenyl	204-210 256-264 284-292	3.886 4.200 4.200
6.	OH ₂	p-nitrophenyl	214 242 276 284	3.861 3.209 3.079 3.792
7.	n-C ₆ H ₇	phenyl	222-223 291 810-812	3.997 4.162 4.189
8.	n-C ₆ H ₇	p-tolyl	222 292 810-812	4.189 4.162 3.977
9.	N-1,1'-(2,2'-Dimethyl-4,4'-biphenyleno)-bis(3-N-hydroxy-3-ethyltriazene)		218 242 368	4.401 4.365 4.581

(b) In compounds no. 5 to 8 an absorption maximum appears in the range 276-292 nm, which may be taken to indicate that there is a greater contribution of the triazene oxide form (II) in these compounds. Disappearance of this band in compounds no. 1 to 4 and 9 is difficult to explain but it seems that a lesser contribution of the hydroxy-triazene form (I) may be responsible for this phenomenon.

(c) In compounds no. 4 to 9 there appears a band in the range 214 to 228 nm and an additional band at 253 ± 11 nm in compounds no. 4, 5, 6 and 9, which may be correlated to the π - π^* band of benzene displaced to the longer wavelengths due to substitution on the benzene ring.

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Preparation and Antibacterial Activities of 2-Aryl-3-[α -(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)benzyl]-4-thiazolidinones

N. C. DESAI, H. K. SHUKLA, N. A. LANGALIA

and

K. A. THAKER

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

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THIAZOLIDINONES, the derivatives of thiazolidine having a carbonyl group at 2, 4 or 5 position, have been studied in detail recently¹⁻³. Several reviews have been written on thiazolidinones which highlight their chemistry and implications⁴⁻¹⁰. The present investigation has been undertaken to compare the effect of azomethines (II) and thiazolidinones (III) on antimycobacterial and antibacterial activity. The 2-aryl-3-[α -(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)benzyl]-4-thiazolidinones (III) have been prepared by the reaction of mercaptoacetic acid with azomethines (II) and tested against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_V), *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

The structure of the title compound (III) has been elucidated on the basis of their elemental analysis, ir and uv spectra. The Schiff bases (II) gave strong band in the region 1630-1615 cm⁻¹, which disappeared by thiazolidine ring formation. The compound III showed $\lambda_{\max}$ at 235, 342 nm and $\nu_{\max}$ at 1630 and 1655 cm⁻¹. The ir spectra were recorded on Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer.

Experimental

α -(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-benzylamine (I) has been prepared following the method described in the literature^{1,4,11}.

Azomethines (II): The appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) and I (0.01 mol) were dissolved in EtOH (95%, 50 ml) and the solution refluxed for 3 h, the excess solvent distilled until the Schiff base commenced to crystallise (Table 1 and 3).

4-Thiazolidinones (III): The mixture of appropriate azomethine (II, 0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) in anhydrous benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h and the excess solvent and thioglycolic acid removed under vacuum. The residue was washed thoroughly with aqueous NaHCO₃ and water, dried and crystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 2 and 3).

Pharmacological screening: The *in vitro* anti-tubercular activity of the compounds I, II and III was studied against H₃₇R_V strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 0.02 mg/ml. The retardation of the growth rate has been studied upto 6 weeks at 37°.

The antibacterial activities of the compounds I, II and III were tested by N-agar pour-plate

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF AZOMETHINES (II)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	(Analysis % N : Found/Calcd.)
1.	C ₆ H ₅	146	4.19 (4.00)
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	176	4.22 (3.96)
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	152	4.21 (3.96)
4.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	162	4.02 (3.76)
5.	4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	95	3.52 (3.31)
6.	5.Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	109	3.66 (3.24)
7.	3,5-di-Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	80	3.04 (2.73)
8.	3,4-OH ₂ .O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	145	3.96 (3.67)
9.	4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	90	6.92 (7.32)
10.	3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	170	6.98 (7.32)
11.	4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	169	4.21 (3.98)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (III)

Sl. No.	R	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
			N	S
1.	C ₆ H ₅	132	3.76 (3.40)	7.99 (7.78)
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	154	3.61 (3.27)	7.95 (7.49)
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	138	3.89 (3.27)	7.98 (7.49)
4.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	154	2.98 (3.14)	7.91 (7.18)
5.	4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	127	3.49 (3.17)	6.91 (7.26)
6.	5-Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	119	2.98 (2.76)	6.59 (6.32)
7.	3,5-di-Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	112	2.78 (2.39)	4.98 (5.47)
8.	3,4-OH ₂ .O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	179	3.32 (3.07)	7.22 (7.03)
9.	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	132	5.98 (6.14)	7.20 (7.01)
10.	3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	200	6.01 (6.14)	7.42 (7.01)
11.	4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	191	3.49 (3.29)	7.72 (7.52)

method in DMF and found to be active against *E.coli* and *S.aureus*.

On comparison of the experimental data, it has been observed that the compounds I and II do not possess significant antimycobacterial activity and the presence of thiazolidine nucleus is necessary for potential antitubercular activity, and the presence of

the halogen atoms in II and III enhances the antibacterial activity.

TABLE 3—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTITUBERCULAR ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS II AND III

Sl. no.	R	Antibacterial activity of II		Antitubercular and antibacterial activity of III		
		Interpretation zone of inhibition at 100 µg concn./disk		Interpretation zone of inhibition at 100 µg concn./disk		Antituberculous activity H ₃₇ R _v
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	
1.	C ₆ H ₅	-	-	-	-	+
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	-	-	+	-	+
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	+	-	-	-	+
4.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	++	-	+	-	+
5.	4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	+	+	+	+	+
6.	5.Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	+	-	+	+	+
7.	3,5-di-Br.2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	++	+	++	+	+
8.	3,4-OH ₂ .O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	+	-	+	-	+
9.	4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	-	-	+	-	+
10.	3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	-	-	-	-	+
11.	4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-	-	+	-	+

(-) = Zone diameter of growth inhibition in mm.
 (+) = Zone diameter less than 20 mm.
 (++) = Zone diameter more than 20 mm.
 The tuberculostatic concentration, 0.03 mg/ml.

